

Iwuamadi's primality test

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Abstract

The formulation of a fast, one-time, and deterministic primality test is the motivation behind this research paper. The main mathematical formulae were researched to achieve the objectives mentioned above. This paper covers theoretical use, while a sister paper would spell the practical applications—theoretical experience is pro rata to practical experience (reality).

1. Introduction

Iwuamadi's primality test is a one-time, deterministic test with ease in identifying primes. The main formulae are from the triangular array below.

Figure 1

$n = \text{row}$; $k = \text{column}$ (position in the n -th row)

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} & & 6 & 16 & 25 & 25 & 16 & 6 \\ k: & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 & 6 \\ n = 6 \end{array}$$

$$\mathbf{T}(n, k) = \mathbf{C}(n, k - 1) + \mathbf{C}(n - 1, k) \quad (1)$$

$\mathbf{T}(n, k) = \text{entry}$

To test whether n is a prime, $n > 2$ and $2 \leq k \leq n - 1$ ($n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$)

In an n -th row, entries ($k = 2$ to $k = n - 1$) begin by subtracting 1 from entry $k = 2$ followed by adding 1 to entry $k = 3$, and alternating others in that order. And if the result of every entry is divisible by the number n , definitely, n is a prime, and if not divisible by number n , n is a composite.

$$\mathbf{R}(n, k) = \mathbf{C}(n, k - 1) + \mathbf{C}(n - 1, k) - (-1)^k \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{R}(n, k) = \text{entry} - (-1)^k \quad (3)$$

$\mathbf{R}(n, k) = \text{result}$ (divided by n)

$k = 3$ is not a factor of $n = 4$, and therefore, the denominator 1 is not a multiple of $k = 3$.

When $n = 5$,
for $k = 2$

$$\frac{11-1}{n} = \frac{10}{5} \\ = \frac{2}{1}$$

$k = 2$ is not a factor of $n = 5$, and therefore, the denominator 1 is not a multiple of $k = 2$;

for $k = 3$,

$$\frac{14+1}{n} = \frac{15}{5} \\ = \frac{3}{1}$$

$k = 3$ is not a factor of $n = 5$, and therefore, the denominator 1 is not a multiple of $k = 3$;

for $k = 4$,

$$\frac{11-1}{n} = \frac{10}{5} \\ = \frac{2}{1}$$

$k = 4$ is not a factor of $n = 5$, and therefore, the denominator 1 is not a multiple of $k = 4$.

Observe the trend with $n = 6, 9, 10, 11$, you will deduce that when n is a composite, where k is a factor, the denominator is always the multiple of k , and where k is not a factor, the denominator is always a nonmultiple of k , and when n is a prime, the denominators are always 1 (a nonmultiple of k).

Therefore, $R(n, k)$ fits the primality test in the triangular array of figure 1. ■

Lemma 2.2:

$$\mathbf{R}\left(n, \frac{n}{2}\right) = \mathbf{C}\left(n, \frac{n}{2} - 1\right) + \mathbf{C}\left(n - 1, \frac{n}{2}\right) - (-1)^{\frac{n}{2}} \quad (5) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{(middle entries when} \\ n \text{ is even)} \end{array}$$

$$R_{me}(n, k) = R\left(n, \frac{n}{2}\right)$$

Proof

When $k = \frac{n}{2}$, where n is even, means, k is a factor of n , and therefore, the denominator will be a multiple of k . Remember, $2 \leq k \leq n - 1$.

Therefore, $R\left(n, \frac{n}{2}\right)$ fits the primality test where n always comes as composite. ■

Lemma 2.3:

$$\mathbf{R}\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2}\right) = \mathbf{C}\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2} - 1\right) + \mathbf{C}\left(n - 1, \frac{n+1}{2}\right) - (-1)^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \quad (6) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{(middle entry} \\ \text{when } n \text{ is odd)} \end{array}$$

$$R_{\text{mo}}(n, k) = R\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2}\right)$$

Proof

$$R(n, k) = T(n, k) - (-1)^k$$

Using $T(n, k)$,

$$\begin{aligned} T(n, k) &= C(n, k-1) + C(n-1, k) \\ &= \frac{n!}{(n-k+1)!(k-1)!} + \frac{(n-1)!}{(n-1-k)!k!} \\ &= \frac{n!k!(n-k-1)! + (n-1)!(k-1)!(n-k+1)!}{(n-k+1)!(k-1)!(n-k-1)!k!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!(k-1)!(n-k-1)!(nk + (n-k+1)(n-k))}{(n-k+1)!(k-1)!(n-k-1)!k!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!(nk + n^2 - nk - nk + k^2 + n - k)}{(n-k+1)!k!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!(n^2 + k^2 - nk + n - k)}{(n-k+1)!k!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!(n(n-k+1) + k(k-1))}{(n-k+1)!k!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!(n^2 - n(k-1) + k(k-1))}{(n-k+1)!k!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!(n^2 + (k-1)(k-n))}{(n-k+1)!k!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!\left(n^2 + \left(\frac{n+1}{2} - 1\right)\left(\frac{n+1}{2} - n\right)\right)}{\left(n - \frac{n+1}{2} + 1\right)!\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!\left(n^2 + \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)\left(\frac{1-n}{2}\right)\right)}{\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)!\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)!} \\ &= \frac{(n-1)!\left(n^2 - \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)^2\right)}{\left(\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)!\right)^2} \end{aligned}$$

When $k = \frac{n+1}{2}$,

$$= \frac{(n-1)! \binom{n+1}{2} \binom{3n-1}{2}}{\left(\binom{n+1}{2}!\right)^2}$$

$\frac{3n-1}{2}$ is a multiplier that forms a linear sequence for n .

$\frac{(n-1)! \binom{n+1}{2}}{\left(\binom{n+1}{2}!\right)^2}$ is the coefficient of $\frac{3n-1}{2}$ with distinct character, which differentiates primes from

composites. $\frac{(n-1)! \binom{n+1}{2}}{\left(\binom{n+1}{2}!\right)^2}$ separately identifies primes (named Iwuamadi's second primality test) without requiring $\frac{3n-1}{2}$.

$$\frac{(n-1)! \binom{n+1}{2}}{\left(\binom{n+1}{2}!\right)^2} + 2(-1)^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \bmod n = 0 \quad (\text{Iwuamadi's second primality test;}$$

n is prime, and prime only, otherwise, n is composite.)

Arrangements and values from $\frac{(n-1)! \binom{n+1}{2}}{\left(\binom{n+1}{2}!\right)^2}$:

For $n = 3$: $\frac{2!}{1!2!} = \frac{2}{2 \times 1}$

For $n = 5$: $\frac{4!}{2!3!} = \frac{3 \times 4}{3 \times 2 \times 1}$

For $n = 7$: $\frac{6!}{3!4!} = \frac{4 \times 5 \times 6}{4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1}$

For $n = 9$: $\frac{8!}{4!5!} = \frac{5 \times 6 \times 7 \times 8}{5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1}$

For $n = 11$: $\frac{10!}{5!6!} = \frac{6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9 \times 10}{6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1}$

For $n = 13$: $\frac{12!}{6!7!} = \frac{7 \times 8 \times 9 \times 10 \times 11 \times 12}{7 \times 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1}$

...

For $n = 25$: $\frac{24!}{12!13!} = \frac{13 \times 14 \times 15 \times 16 \times 17 \times 18 \times 19 \times 20 \times 21 \times 22 \times 23 \times 24}{13 \times 12 \times 11 \times 10 \times 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1}$

Apply the dividend-divisor pair to the arrangements above beginning from the far right. It would be observed that when n is a composite, in at least a pair (apart from divisor = 1), divisor of a pair is a factor of its corresponding dividend, and when n is a prime, no pair has a divisor as a factor apart from divisor = 1. Divisibility in dividend-divisor pairs associated with composites makes it impossible for composites to behave as primes in $\mathbb{R}\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2}\right)$. ■

3. Main results

$$R\left(n, \frac{n}{2}\right) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{n} \quad (n \text{ is a composite}) \quad (7)$$

When:

$$R\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{n} \quad (n \text{ is a prime}) \quad (8)$$

$$R\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2}\right) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{n} \quad (n \text{ is a composite}) \quad (9)$$

4. Applications

1. $R\left(n, \frac{n}{2}\right) \pmod{n}$ (one-time trial)

$$R\left(n, \frac{n}{2}\right) \pmod{n} \neq 0 \quad (n \text{ is a composite}) \quad (10)$$

2. $R\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2}\right) \pmod{n}$ (one-time trial)

$$R\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2}\right) \pmod{n} = 0 \quad (n \text{ is a prime}) \quad (11)$$

$$R\left(n, \frac{n+1}{2}\right) \pmod{n} \neq 0 \quad (n \text{ is a composite}) \quad (12)$$

5. Conclusion

Iwuamadi's primality test has been theoretically tested, and awaits its speed (operating time).

Reference

Mahavira. 850/1912. *Ganita-sara-sangraha of Mahāvīrācārya with English translation and notes* (M. Rangacharya, Translated & Edited). Government Press.